

ISic3585

Honours for Iulia Soaemias

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe

Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2019-07-16 - Jonathan Prag edited the file based on autopsy and study for 2017 edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Presumed to be from the agora excavations

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory 30601

Physical Description

A slab of pink-white marble, broken into numerous small fragments, of which some are missing; the fragments have subsequently been floated into place and the gaps filled with plaster, and the missing letters / parts of letters traced in the plaster.

Dimensions

Height 78 cm
Width 76.5 cm
Depth 2.8 cm

Layout

Seven lines of Latin text are mostly preserved, filling the vertical space, but with extensive margins to left and right.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letters are simply carved, tall V-cut capitals, with thick, short serifs.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-4: 58-72 mm
Lines 5-7: 38-57 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: not measured mm

Text

1. Iul̄iae Sōa,ę
2. midi · Aug(ustae)
3. matri imp(eratoris)
4. Caes(aris) M(arci) · Au
5. reli Antoni
6. ŋ,ĭ Pii Fel(icis) · Aug(usti)
7. D(ecreto) D(ecurionum) P(ecunia) P(ublica)

Apparatus

Text from autopsy, after initial reconstruction by Scibona

Translation (en)

To Iulia Soaemias Augusta, mother of Emperor Caesar Marcus Aurelius Antoninus Pius Felix Augustus, by decree of the town councillors, at public expense.

Commentary

A number of the letters only survive partially on the original stone fragments; the dotted letters in the transcription are those where, if the plaster restoration were to be removed, the surviving traces would be insufficient without context and parallels to restore them with certainty. The overall reading and restoration, however, appears to be certain.

The use of interpuncts is very irregular, and this is not a result simply of missing fragments, although it is possible that interpuncts are lost in several places such as between DD and PP in the final line.

The desire of the engraver to maintain the left and right margins of the text as a visual feature within the larger space of the slab is notable, and results in several awkward line divisions in the middle of names.

Iulia Soaemias (Bassiana) (Herzog, RE 10.1 (1919), s.v. Iulia no.596, col.948-951) was the mother of the Emperor Elagabalus. She regularly has the titles of Augusta and Mater Augusti, although the precise variation here of mater Imp. Caes. is not well attested (Cf. CIL 6 no.40679 [www.trismegistos.org/text/264004] ; CIL 8 no.2564 [www.trismegistos.org/text/204905] ; CIL 8 no.2715 [www.trismegistos.org/text/323374] ; AE 1987 no.1130 [www.trismegistos.org/text/204416] ; AE 1928 no.36 [www.trismegistos.org/text/205390]).

The names and titles date the text to 218-222 AD.

As with the honorific inscription for C. Fulvius Plautianus (ISic3584 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3584>]), it is notable that this inscription has not suffered from damnatio memoriae, to which a number of the inscriptions for Iulia Soaemias were subject.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645664

Bibliography

Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. *Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa*. Palermo. At no.27

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Photo J.Prag courtesy Soprintendenza BBCCAA di Messina